

On δ -Small Pseudo Projective Modules

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Abstract

In this paper we give three new concepts, a concepts of δ -Small pseudo projective module, δ -small quasi projective and δ -small pseudo stable module, these concepts are generalization of Pseudo Projective modules, quasi projective module and pseudo stable module respectively we will study these concepts and give some results.

Keywords: δ -Small pseudo projective module; δ -small quasi projective module; δ -small pseudo stable module.

حول المقاسات الإسقاطية الزائفة من النمط δ الصغير

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الخلاصة

في هذا البحث نعطي ثلاث مفاهيم جديده ومفهوم المقاس الإسقاطي الزائف من النوع δ الصغير ومفهوم المقاس الإسقاطي الظاهري من النوع δ الصغير, ومفهوم المقاس الإسقاطي شبه المستقر من النوع δ الصغير . هذه المفاهيم هي تعميم لمفاهيم المقاس الإسقاطي الزائف والمقاس الظاهري بالمقاس الإسقاطي شبه المستقر على التوالي. سندرس هذه المفاهيم ونعطي بعض النتائج.

1. Introduction

All rings in this paper are commutative rings with identity, and all modules are unitary left R-modules. Let M be an R-module. A submodule A of M is called essential if every nonzero submodule of M has a nonzero intersection with A , [1]. If A is a submodule of M , then the annihilator of A is defined as $Ann(A) = \{r \in R \mid rA = 0\}$, [1]. If M is R-module, then $Z(M) = \{x \in M : Ann(A) \subseteq_e R\}$ is called the singular submodule of M . If $Z(M) = M$, then M is called the singular module, [1]. A submodule A of M is called c-singular if M/A is a singular module [2]. A submodule N of a module M is called δ -small in M if for every c-singular submodule L of M , the equality $N + L = M$ implies $L = M$, [2]. A non-zero module M is δ -hollow, if every proper submodule is δ -small in M , [3]. Let P and M be an R-module. Then P is called M -projective, if for any epimorphism $g: M \rightarrow N$ and any homomorphism $f: P \rightarrow N$, there exists a homomorphism $h: P \rightarrow M$ such that $g \circ h = f$, [4]. An R-module M is called quasi projective module if M is M -projective module, [5]. An R-module M is called pseudo projective if for any given module A and epimorphisms $f: M \rightarrow A$ and $g: M \rightarrow A$, there exists an h in $End(M)$ such that $f = g \circ h$, [6]. A submodule N of an R-module M is said to be pseudo stable if for every two epimorphisms $f, g: M \rightarrow A$, with $N \subseteq Ker g \cap Ker f$ there exists h in $End(M)$ such that $f = g \circ h$, then $h(N) \subseteq N$, [6]. A submodule A of an R-module M is called fully invariant if $f(A) \subseteq A$ for all $f \in End(M)$. If every submodule of

M is fully invariant, then M is called a duo-module, [7]. Let M and N be R -modules. An epimorphism $g: M \rightarrow N$ is said to be δ -small epimorphism, if $\ker g \ll_{\delta} M$, [8].

2. Preliminary Notes

Definition (2.1): An R -module M is said to be δ -small quasi projective if for any given module A , any δ -small epimorphism $g: M \rightarrow A$, any homomorphism $f: M \rightarrow A$ can be lifted to an endomorphism h of M such that the following diagram is commutative;

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & & M \\
 & \swarrow \text{---} & \downarrow \\
 h & & f \\
 & \swarrow & \downarrow \\
 M & \xrightarrow{g} & A \longrightarrow 0, \ker g \ll_{\delta} M
 \end{array}$$

$$\text{i.e. } g \circ h = f.$$

Definition (2.2): An R -module M is said δ -small pseudo projective module if for any module A , with δ -small epimorphism $g: M \rightarrow A$ and epimorphism $f: M \rightarrow A$, there exists an $h \in \text{End}(M)$ such that the following diagram is commutative:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & & M \\
 & \swarrow \text{---} & \downarrow \\
 h & & f \\
 & \swarrow & \downarrow \\
 M & \xrightarrow{g} & A \longrightarrow 0, \ker g \ll_{\delta} M \\
 & & \downarrow \\
 & & 0
 \end{array}$$

$$\text{i.e. } g \circ h = f.$$

Definition (2.3): A submodule N of an R -module M is said to be δ -small pseudo stable module if for any epimorphism $f: M \rightarrow A$ and any δ -small epimorphism $g: M \rightarrow A$ with $N \subseteq \ker g \cap \ker f$, there exists $h \in \text{End}(M)$ such that $f = g \circ h$, then $h(N) \subseteq N$.

Examples (2.4):

1. Z_2 as Z -module is δ -small quasi projective but not projective.
2. Q as Z -module is not quasi projective.
3. Z_6 as Z -module is δ -small pseudo projective but not projective.
- 4.
- 5.

3. Main Results

Proposition (3.1): Let M be a δ -hollow module the following are equivalent:

- (i) M is δ -small pseudo projective.
- (ii) M is pseudo projective.

Proof: (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Let M be a δ -small pseudo projective module and A be any module. and $f, g : M \rightarrow A$ are epimorphisms. Since M is δ -hollow module, then $\ker g$ is δ -small submodule of M , So g is δ -small epimorphism. Thus, by (i) there exist a homomorphism h in $\text{End}(M)$ such that $f = g \circ h$, therefore M is pseudo projective.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) clear from definition.

Proposition (3.2): Let M be a δ -small pseudo projective module and $g : M \rightarrow N$ be a δ -small epimorphism then there exists a homomorphism h in $\text{End}(M)$ such that $\ker g = \ker(g \circ h)$ is δ -small pseudo stable under h .

Proof: Since $g : M \rightarrow N$ is δ -small epimorphism, then $M/\ker g \cong N$. Let $g^* : M/\ker g \rightarrow N$ be an isomorphism, Let $\pi : M \rightarrow M/\ker g$ be the natural epimorphism. Since M is δ -small pseudo projective, then there exists a homomorphism h in $\text{End}(M)$ such that the following diagram commutative:

i.e. $g^* \circ \pi = g \circ h$.

Now, let $x \in \ker g \Rightarrow x \in \ker \pi \Rightarrow \pi(x) = 0$

$$\Rightarrow g^* \circ \pi(x) = 0 \Rightarrow g \circ h(x) = 0 \Rightarrow x \in \ker g \circ h \Rightarrow \ker g \subseteq \ker g \circ h$$

On the other hand if $y \in \ker g \circ h \Rightarrow g \circ h(y) = 0 \Rightarrow g^* \circ \pi(y) = 0 \Rightarrow \pi(y) \in \ker g^*$ and since g^* is one - one $\Rightarrow \pi(y) = 0 \Rightarrow y \in \ker \pi = \ker g$. Therefore $\ker g = \ker g \circ h$.

Now, let $z \in \ker g \Rightarrow g(z) = 0 \Rightarrow g \circ h(z) = 0 \Rightarrow g(h(z) - z) = 0 \Rightarrow h(z) - z \in \ker g \Rightarrow h(z) \in \ker g \Rightarrow h(\ker g) \subseteq \ker g$.

Proposition (3.3): Let M be a δ -small pseudo projective module, K be a δ -small submodule of M if K is stable under $\text{End}(M)$, then M/K is δ -small pseudo projective.

Proof: Let $f : M/K \rightarrow A$ be an epimorphism, $g : M/K \rightarrow A$ be a δ -small epimorphism and $v : M \rightarrow M/K$ be the natural epimorphism where A is any R - module. Since M is δ -small pseudo projective Then there exist h in $\text{End}(M)$ such that the following diagram commutative:

i.e. $g \circ v \circ h = f \circ v$. Define $h^*: M/K \rightarrow M/K$ by $h^*(x + K) = h(x) + K$. It's clear that h^* is well defined and homomorphism.

Now $h^* \circ v = v \circ h \Rightarrow g \circ h^* \circ v = g \circ v \circ h \Rightarrow g \circ h^* \circ v = f \circ v$

But v is onto $\Rightarrow g \circ h^* = f$, thus M/K is δ -small pseudo projective.

Proposition (3.4): Let M be a δ -small pseudo projective module and $g: M \rightarrow N$ be a δ -small epimorphism, then N is δ -small pseudo projective.

Proof: Since $g: M \rightarrow N$ is an epimorphism, then $M/\ker g \cong N$, but $M/\ker g$ is δ -small pseudo projective (Proposition 3.3), therefore N is δ -small pseudo projective.

Proposition (3.5): If T is a δ -small pseudo stable submodule of a δ -small quasi projective module Q and A is a submodule of T , then T/A is a δ -small pseudo stable submodule of Q/A .

Proof: Let $f: Q/A \rightarrow B$ be epimorphism, $g: Q/A \rightarrow B$ be a δ -small epimorphism with $T/A \subseteq \ker f \cap \ker g$ such that there exists h in $\text{End}(Q/A)$ satisfying $f = g \circ h$. Let $v: Q \rightarrow Q/A$ be the natural epimorphism, then since Q is δ -small quasi projective, there exists a homomorphism h^* in $\text{End}(Q)$ such that the following diagram commutative:

i.e. $h \circ v = v \circ h^* \Rightarrow f \circ v = g \circ h \circ v = g \circ v \circ h^*$.

Since we have $f \circ v(T) = f(T/A) = 0$

and $g \circ v(T) = g(T/A) = 0$.

Therefore $T \subseteq \ker f \circ v \cap \ker g \circ v$. But T is δ -small pseudo stable and hence $h^*(T) \subseteq T$. It follows that $h(T/A) = h \circ v(T) = v \circ h^*(T) \subseteq v(T) = T/A$.

Thus T/A is δ -small pseudo stable submodule of Q/A .

Proposition (3.6): Let Q be a δ -small quasi projective module and T be a δ -small pseudo stable submodule of Q . If C containing T , is not a δ -small pseudo stable submodule of Q , then C/T is not a δ -small pseudo stable submodule of Q/T .

Proof: Let $h : Q \rightarrow A$ be an epimorphism, $g : Q \rightarrow A$ be a δ -small epimorphism and Let C be not δ -small pseudo stable in Q , then there exists $f \in \text{End}(Q), C \subseteq \text{ker}g \cap \text{ker}h$ with following diagram is commutative:

i.e. $h = g \circ f$ such that $f(x) \notin C$ for some $x \in C$. Let $v : Q \rightarrow Q/T$ be the natural epimorphism.

Define $F : Q/T \rightarrow Q/T$ by $F(q + T) = f(q) + T$. so $F \circ v = v \circ f$.

Its clear that F is well define and homomorphism. And $F(x + T) = f(x) + T \notin C/T$. Now since $T \subseteq \text{ker}g \cap \text{ker}h$, then there exists G and H in $\text{Hom}(Q/T, A)$ such that $g = G \circ v$ and $h = H \circ v$. since g and h are epimorphism, so G and H are epimorphism.

Now $h = g \circ f \Rightarrow H \circ v = G \circ v \circ f = G \circ F \circ v$. And since v is epimorphism therefore $H = G \circ F$. So we have $H(C/T) = H \circ v(C) = h(C) = 0$, similary $G(C/T) = 0$. Therefore $C/T \subseteq \text{ker}H \cap \text{ker}G$. But $F(x + T) \notin C/T$. And hence C/T is not δ -small pseudo stable.

Proposition (3.7): Let M be a δ -small pseudo projective module, $g : M \rightarrow N$ is any δ -small epimorphism, then $\text{Ker}g$ is a δ -small pseudo stable submodule of M .

Proof: Since $g : M \rightarrow N$ be a δ -small epimorphism, then $M/\text{ker}g \cong N$, Let $g^* : M/\text{ker}g \rightarrow N$ be an isomorphism, $f : M \rightarrow M/\text{ker}g$ be the natural epimorphism, then $\text{ker}g \subseteq \text{ker}g \cap \text{ker}g^* \circ f$. since M is δ -small pseudo projective, there exists h in $\text{End}(M)$ such that the following diagram commutatives:

$$\text{i.e. } g^* \circ f = g \circ h.$$

Now, if $h(\ker g) \not\subseteq \ker g$, then there exists $x \in \ker g$ such that $h(x) \in h(\ker g)$ and $h(x) \notin \ker g$.

Now $0 \neq g \circ h(x) = g^* \circ f(x) = 0$, which is a contradiction, since $\ker g \subseteq \ker g^* \circ f$, thus $\ker g$ is δ -small pseudo stable.

Proposition (3.8): Let M be a δ -small pseudo projective module, A and B be invariant submodules of M . Then $A \cap B$ is a δ -small pseudo stable submodule of M if either A or B is δ -small in M .

Proof: Let A be δ -small in M , $g: M/A \rightarrow T$ be any δ -small epimorphism, $f: M/A \rightarrow T$ be any epimorphism, where T is any R -module and $v: M \rightarrow M/A$ be the natural epimorphism. Then $A \cap B \subseteq \ker g \circ v \cap \ker f \circ v$. Since M is δ -small pseudo projective, then there exists h in $\text{End}(M)$ such that the following diagram commutates:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 & & & & M & & \\
 & & & & \downarrow v & & \\
 & & & & \downarrow f & & \\
 h & & M/A & & & & \\
 & \swarrow & & & & & \\
 & M & \xrightarrow{g} & M/A & \xrightarrow{g} & T & \xrightarrow{g} & 0 \\
 v & & & & & \downarrow & & \\
 & & & & & 0 & &
 \end{array}$$

i.e. $f \circ v = g \circ v \circ h$. now since $h(A \cap B) \subseteq h(A) \subseteq A$ and $h(A \cap B) \subseteq h(B) \subseteq B$ since A and B are invariant submodules, Thus $h(A \cap B) \subseteq A \cap B$. Hence $A \cap B$ is δ -small pseudo stable.

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